

ENTERPRISE: PERFORMANCE AND BUSINESS PROCESSES

**DATA QUALITY AND ACCOUNTING
INFORMATION SYSTEMS: ACTUAL
PERFORMANCE IN ALBANIA**

ERJON ZOTO

*Faculty of Economy,
University of Tirana
Arben Broci str., Tirana 1000, Albania*

JEL CLASSIFICATIONS: M40

KEYWORDS: Accounting information systems, data quality, performance

ABSTRACT: Data quality is crucial in today's business processes, as it is generally associated with the set of data fit for use by data consumers - the persons that access, interpret and use data during their work activity. On the other hand, data quality is very important for the Accounting Information Systems' (AIS) success, where AIS is a computer-based system that processes financial data and supports the decision making processes inside the organization. There are empirical evidences showing that data quality level in AIS has been and will always be problematic. Their interrelationship is dependant of several factors, including technical capacities or even the level of teamwork in an organization. This paper tries to analyze the actual performance of the factors influencing in the process of data quality in AIS used from organizations in Albania. The results will be compared with state-of-art literature review regarding the factors perceived as critical factors in ensuring data quality in AIS, giving way to some important concluding remarks.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.15208/pieb.2014.04>

Vol.14 (1), PP.34-41

Source: Zoto E., 2014. "Data quality and accounting information systems: Actual performance in Albania," *Perspectives of Innovations, Economics & Business*, Vol.14(1), pp.34-41, <http://dx.doi.org/10.15208/pieb.2014.04>

Introduction

Problems related to the quality of data rise from different issues. These problems may be severe enough to interrupt the business processes inside an organization or even impede it to follow the procedures required by the law, implying considerable monetary losses. Some of the main problems regarding data quality include missing data, uncategorized or misinterpreted attributes, duplicates or even incorrect data models.

Instead of just correcting these problems, the best approach towards avoiding them would be to understand first their causes and then to define the proper procedures that should prevent them from occurring in the future.

There is a high demand for qualitative data management, while data processing has moved from supporting operations in a business organization towards being an operation itself, as important as, or even more important than the other existing

operations. The qualitative data management cannot be achieved without a proper data quality policy and without proper knowledge over the factors that influence data quality, focusing on the data flowing inside AIS.

Some of the factors are related to organizational issues, others are more IT-related. A thorough analysis of these factors is needed if one takes in consideration recent developments in the business field. Understanding the level of performance of these factors is also important as it gives important insights for business representatives towards finding the best approach for improving the overall level of data quality inside their organizations.

Among them, some factors have been successfully applied more than others, or at least they are perceived as being such. Thus, this paper focuses on showing the actual performance of the factors influencing data quality in AIS, related to the business environment in Albania. An important part of the paper shall include the most achieved factors among all, as an important fact of today's reality. All results included in this paper derive from a related survey developed recently.

Literature review

As mentioned before, data quality is mainly explained by associating it with the data fit for use by data consumers (Huang et al., 1999). Though the concepts of data and information are not identical, several authors use information quality in order to define data quality and vice versa. Thus, English (1999) extended the definition above, stating that information quality is related to the following:

1. All expectations of knowledge workers¹ and end consumers² are continuously met in all quality characteristics of the information products and services, needed to accomplish the enterprise mission (internal knowledge worker) or personal objectives (end consumer).
2. The degree to which information consistently meets the requirements and expectations of all knowledge workers who require it to perform their processes.

Data quality is also defined from its related dimensions. There are several dimensions related, among whom the most important and generally accepted are the following (Ballou et al., 1982; 1985; 1987; 1993):

- *Accuracy*: when the recorded value is in conformity with the actual value
- *Timeliness*: when the value is recorded in time, not out of date
- *Completeness*: when all the values are recorded
- *Consistency*: when all the values are represented in the same way.

Meanwhile, several authors have tried to build a general model for data quality analysis. This model is composed of seven elements (Wang et al., 1995):

- *Management responsibilities*: the development of a strategy related to the data quality inside the corporation and the implementation of a data quality system;

¹ Highly skilled professionals who are involved in the non-routine production, interpretation, and application of complex information.

² The persons or organizations whose needs a product or service provider must meet, and whose satisfaction with its products and services, including information, determines enterprise success or failure. A customer may be a direct, immediate Customer or the End-consumer of the product or service.

- *Operational and assurance costs*: operating costs include prevention, evaluation and failure costs, while assurance costs include expenses made for demonstrating and proving the quality level required by customers and managers;
- *Research and development*: the definition of data quality dimensions and the measurement of their values, analysis and design of data quality aspects and the design of data manufacturing systems that include these aspects;
- *Production*: the quality requirements in the procurement of raw data components and elements required for the production of data, the assessment of the quality level for the raw data, work-in-progress and final data and the identification of non-conforming data items;
- *Distribution*: the processes of storage, identification, assembling, installing, delivering and after-sales services for data, the documentation of quality and quality records for several data products;
- *Employee's management*: employee awareness for issues related to data quality, motivating employees in order to produce high quality data and measuring the achievement of the quality level;
- *Legal functions*: the safety level and liabilities that occur from the data produced.

On the other hand, a relevant research from English (1999) defines the main factors that would influence data quality as the following:

- Understanding the meaning of information quality improvement and why should be done;
- Implementing this improvement in an effective way;
- Implementing the information quality improvement for the right problem;
- Training and communication;
- Offering incentives if a certain level of information quality is achieved;
- Management commitment towards the information quality improvement, considering it as an important management tool;
- Managing change.

As mentioned earlier, achieving and ensuring data quality should be a continuous process. In this way, organizations should need certain steps to follow in order to achieve a certain level of data quality. Firth (1999) stated four necessary steps for initiating and implementing a successful data quality process in a certain system, as mentioned below:

1. Establish a data quality position;
2. Formulate a data quality strategy;
3. Determine objectives;
4. Achieve management commitment and employee commitment.

Understanding the relation between data quality and AIS in general brings the necessity of understanding what AIS is. There are several definitions regarding AIS. It may be seen as a subsystem of Management Information Systems, as noted by Uday and Wiggins (1999), whereas its main function is processing financial transactions, and non financial ones that influence directly in the processing of the first ones, as shown by Hall (1998), who also divided an AIS into four subsystems explained further below:

- *The transaction processing system*, which supports daily business operations, associated with documents and many messages transmitted towards users inside the organization;

- *The general ledger or the financial reporting system*, which produces traditional financial statements, such as income statements, balance sheets, statements of cash flows and other reports required by law;
- *Fixed assets system*, which processes transactions related to acquisition, maintenance and selling of fixed assets;
- *Management reporting system*, which prepares for the internal management staff special purpose financial reports and other information needed for decision making, such as budgeting or responsibility reports.

When ensuring an acceptable level of data quality in AIS it is important to find the main factors that influence this process. Identifying these factors would be very useful for the business environment, but still rather unclear at present. Several researchers have worked in this context, while an important contribution in determining the main factors that influence data quality in AIS was made from H. J. Xu (2003), who managed to identify the factors mentioned below:

- *Top management commitment*: the top management should understand data quality and support activities related to this process;
- *AIS characteristics*: the existence of proper and useful systems;
- *Input control*: getting the right information from the beginning, to prevent errors;
- *Employee capabilities*: hiring trained, qualified and highly experienced staff in all levels, from the top level towards the lowest one inside the organization. The employees must be skillful and with a high level of technical knowledge and business knowledge;
- *Team working (communication)*: a proper teamwork and communication between and among different departments, and among different professionals from IT and accounting;
- *Middle management commitment*: accepting the responsibility from middle management for data quality and having effective procedures implemented at this management level.

A similar study extended the list of factors above, giving a new point of view on the subject, as shown below (Zoto, Tole, 2014):

- *Training*: it may be in the initial phases and also continuous, helping to create an adapt working staff for achieving a better overall data quality performance
- *AIS characteristics*
- *Knowledge over AIS and Data Quality*: understanding how the systems work and understanding the importance of data quality and its relationship to the organization objectives
- *Control over Data Quality*
- *Continuous Improvement*
- *Staff skills*
- *AIS audit*
- *Internal Controls*

The survey

The survey starts with general questions, regarding the respondents' role related to AIS, the type of AIS used in the organization where they are employed and the years of experience they have with AIS. In the same section, the respondents are asked to evaluate the overall level of data quality in AIS, regarding the system they have

worked for, starting from “Very low” (equaled to 1) up to “Very high” (equaled to 5). Then they are asked to evaluate in the same way the four dimensions of data quality, as mentioned above.

In the next section, the survey comprises questions regarding all factors that were considered from existing literature relevant for determining the level of data quality in AIS. Some of the factors are separated in several sub factors, being that the level of relevance between them might be different. For each factor, the respondents are required to evaluate the relevance of the factor, from “Not relevant” (equaled with 1) up to “Highly relevant” (equaled with 5), and then the actual level of its establishment in the organization, from “Not established” (equaled with 1) to “Very good” (equaled with 5). This section includes in the end a part determining the most relevant factors and the most established among the ones evaluated in the upper level of the section.

The survey sample included individuals, chosen as professionals in the field of Accounting and IT - as the closest fields related to AIS - with a certain level of experience regarding these systems, as was further shown by the sample results. The accounting professionals chosen are part of the official institutions representing them in Albania, while IT professionals are generally IT managers in several organizations or other professionals, knowledgeable about the issues of data quality in AIS.

They were mainly reached by e-mail and further asked to fill out the online form of the questionnaire. The online form made it possible to have all necessary information from the respondents provided in the right way by using several validation methods. Besides, a certain number of questionnaires were prepared in a printed form and distributed to a certain part of the sample so as to be filled out manually.

The total sample included 700 individuals and the total number of respondents reached the level of 175, which indicates a 25% response rate. The years of experience with AIS ranged from 1 year or less up to 34 years dealing with several AIS, including manual ones. The average experience was more than 5 years.

Respondents have dealt with several types of AIS, where the majority has worked with systems built domestically, represented from the products related to Alpha, Financa 5 and Bilanc systems. Other systems to be mentioned include SAP, OpenERP, Navision etc., which are globally known systems and recently adopted from the companies operating in Albania. Besides, the vast majority of respondents have worked with computer-based AIS, whereas only a few, 2-3, have worked with manual systems. The respondents had relatively an average to good opinion related to the overall quality of AIS they had knowledge about, as shown below (Table 1).

TABLE 1. RATING OVERALL DATA QUALITY AND RELATED DIMENSIONS

	Overall quality	Accuracy	Timeliness	Fullness	Consistency
Very low	0	0	0	0	0
Low	1	2	7	5	4
Average	89	52	58	76	75
High	73	100	89	77	76
Very high	12	21	21	17	20

Source: Zoto and Tole, 2014.

The next section gave important insights regarding the most achieved factors affecting data quality in AIS. As the results show, the most important factors according to the ratings are listed below (Table 2). The ten factors mentioned above were ranked according to their overall average rating, considering all values related to each factor and corresponding sub factors. Taking into account the top three of them, the results show that, for the sample taken, data quality in AIS is being achieved by

using in the best way the working staff skills, which is the most achieved factor. Data quality is also supported from the characteristics of the chosen AIS inside the organizations of the sample. The third most achieved factor is related to the level of overall knowledge over AIS and data quality, stressing the fact that a well-trained staff with the proper knowledge guarantees a good level of data quality in AIS.

TABLE 2. TOP TEN FACTORS, ACCORDING TO AVERAGE RATING

Rank	Factor	Average Rating
1	Staff skills	3.85
2	Characteristics of AIS	3.78
3	Knowledge over AIS and data quality	3.76
4	Measurement and Reporting	3.73
5	Control over Data Quality	3.72
6	Input Control	3.72
7	Workplace	3.72
8	Managerial commitment	3.71
9	Internal controls	3.70
10	Fulfilling system users' requests	3.68

Source: Zoto and Tole, 2014.

Following factors include measurement and reporting, control over data quality and input controls. Measurement and reporting issues are very important for the process of data quality since they help define what the main indicators that define qualitative data are and they are also related to the level of awareness regarding data quality problems. Control over data quality is also an important process that should be implemented carefully, and its positioning in the top 5 achieved factors shows that Albanian organizations in general have a positive approach towards implementing them. Input controls are also very important for data quality, as shown also from recent studies, and their impact seems to be well-known in the Albanian business environment too.

TABLE 3. TOP TEN FACTORS, ACCORDING TO TOTAL RANKINGS

Rank	Factor	Total rankings
1	Characteristics of AIS	56
2	Internal Controls	45
3	Training	39
4	Established Policies and Rules over Data Quality	38
5	Measurement and Reporting	37
6	Knowledge over AIS and data quality	31
7	Managerial commitment	26
8	AIS audit	25
9	Teamwork	25
10	Change management	19

Source: Zoto and Tole, 2014.

Other factors mentioned in the table above include workplace, managerial commitment, internal controls and fulfilling system users' requests. When an AIS is chosen as adapt to users' requests, the users are more satisfied with the system and the system is set to be more user-friendly than the other options. This will also effect in the overall level of data quality, since a lot of problems for data quality are related to human errors. A suitable and cozy workplace along with the proper managerial commitment towards data quality is also needed inside an organization. When these factors are among the most achieved ones, seems that the organization is performing

well against data quality. Internal controls are part of the routine processes inside an organization, and they are also part of the most important factors regarding data quality.

The survey made possible another approach towards finding the most achieved factors by asking the respondents to individually rank the top three factors they perceived as most achieved. Considering this approach, the table below shows the overall results (Table 3). In the table above, the values in total rankings show the total of times the corresponding factor or related sub factors were included in the list of the top three most achieved factors

Considering the results shown in the last two tables, there seems to be a consistency among five of the top factors listed below:

- *Characteristics of AIS*
- *Knowledge over AIS and Data Quality*
- *Measurement and Reporting*
- *Managerial commitment*
- *Internal controls*

Surprisingly, the ranking position for four of the above is almost the same in both tables, whereas for internal controls, the respondents' perception for them is that they are among the most achieved, while the level of importance is slightly lower than the other factors included in the most important factors.

The factors listed above state the actual measures that organizations are taking in order to ensure an acceptable level of data quality. The process of data quality seems to be supported from the managerial team, and is being monitored through several internal controls and frequent reporting. Organizations know that AIS affects data quality, and trying to minimize its negative effects means imposing some rules and learning procedures over AIS and how to achieve data quality. The characteristics of AIS are crucial as a starting point to consider the value of AIS and its support for data quality inside the organization.

Literature shows that the characteristics of AIS and internal controls are amongst the most important factors affecting data quality in AIS, along with the knowledge regarding AIS and data quality. It seems that organizations should make more progress towards training their employees regarding AIS they shall use and should evaluate their skills as related to their objectives for data quality. Organizations should also perform more focused controls related to data quality and AIS, including AIS audit procedures, preferably with the support of third parties.

Conclusion

Data quality has been a continuous problem in the organizations where data and information is a crucial asset for daily activities. Different organizations have found different approaches in order to achieve an acceptable level of data quality. When considered the relationship between data quality and AIS, the analysis is more complex, as data quality affects the procedures inside AIS, but also AIS procedures and characteristics affect the level of data quality inside the organization, as shown by the literature.

When organizations find what's more important to do in order to have a qualitative set of data input and produced from their AIS, the managerial team shall have the right tools in order to improve it, thus increasing the overall performance.

This paper gave proper insights regarding the factors that are most achieved in the Albanian business environment. The results were taken from a related survey, which was designed to give important information related to the issues studied.

As stated from the results, the factors with the highest level of performance include among others issues related to the characteristics of AIS, knowledge over AIS and data quality, measurement and reporting, managerial commitment and internal controls. These factors were found to be mostly present in all respondents' assessments regarding top factors realized.

Apparently, the literature shows that not all the factors perceived as most important regarding data quality in AIS have been achieved more than others, stressing the fact that data quality is a continuous process that should always be monitored and supported from different kinds of view.

The analysis supported from this paper uses a simple statistical approach, but could be developed more when taking into account the recent developments in the field of Information Technology (IT). Recently, computer systems are being provided with extraordinary abilities towards performing detailed analysis of problems of all kinds.

Intelligent techniques have been introduced, capable of classifying different situations and problems considering several other parameters related to them. These techniques cover several fields related to Artificial Intelligence (AI), including decision trees, neural networks etc. AI techniques could be a useful tool for supporting the results of the survey above, as they are considered suitable for predicting trends and patterns in large data sets, with a high level of accuracy. Thus, they may be appropriate for supporting or refuting the results from the study above.

References

- Huang HT, Lee YW and Wang RY, 1999. *Quality information and knowledge*, Prentice Hall, New Jersey
- Huang HT, Lee YW and Wang RY, 1999. *Quality information and knowledge*, Prentice Hall, New Jersey
- Ballou DP and Pazer HL, 1982. "The impact of inspector fallibility on the inspection policy serial production system," *Management Science*, Vol. 28, No.4: 387-399, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.28.4.387>
- Ballou DP and Pazer HL, 1985. "Modeling data and process quality in multi-input, multi-output information systems," *Management Science*, Vol.31, No.2: 150-162, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.31.2.150>
- Ballou DP, Belardo S, Klein B, 1987. "Implication of data quality for spreadsheet analysis", *DataBase*, Vol.18, No.3: 13-19
- Ballou DP, Wang RY, Pazer HL and Tayi KG, 1993. *Modeling data manufacturing systems to determine data product quality*, Total data quality management research program, MIT Sloan School of Management, (No. TDQM- 93-09), Cambridge, MA
- Firth C, 1996. *Data quality in practice: Experience from the frontline*, in *Proceedings of Conference of Information Quality*
- Hall JA, 1998. *Accounting information systems*, 2nd ed., South-Western College Publishing
- Uday S. M., and E. Wiggins Casper, J., 1999. A Perspective on accounting information systems research, *Journal of Information Systems*, 13(1): 3-6, <http://dx.doi.org/10.2308/jis.1999.13.1.3>
- Wang RY, Storey, VC, Firth CP, 1995. A framework for analysis of data quality research, *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*, Vol.7, No.4: 623-639, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/69.404034>
- Xu H, 2003. *Critical success factors for accounting information systems data quality*
- Zoto E, Tole, Dh, 2014. "The main factors that influence data quality in accounting information systems", *IJSINT*, Vol.1, Tirana